

CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PURE LEAD COMPOSITE USED FOR TUBULAR POSITIVE GRID IN LEAD-ACID BATTERY

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ABSTRACT

A new type of positive grid of the Lead-Acid Battery, carbon fiber reinforced pure lead composite grid, had been prepared by vacuum liquid infiltration method. The design and the process of the new grid were discussed in detail. Comparing with the conventional grid made of Pb-6% Sb alloy, the strength of the new grid increases by 2 times, whereas its weight decreases by more than 35%, furthermore, its capacity increases by more than 10%.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers have superior conductivity and corrosion resistance in sulfuric acid, besides its high specific strength and modulus. It has been verified that carbon fiber can be used as a reinforcer to make positive grid of Lead-Acid Battery^{1,2,3}. The paper proposed a good method of using C/Pb composite material to fabricate positive grid of Lead-Acid Battery, by which satisfactory grid products can be obtained.

DESIGN AND PROCESS

1. Material

The carbon fibers made in Shanghai Carbon Factory were used as reinforcer, whose tensile strength and modulus are 2320 MPa and 222 GPa respectively. Pure lead, coming from commercial supply and with purity more than 99.99%, was selected as matrix.

2. Choice of carbon fiber volume fraction

The grid used in battery is not only for supporter, but also current conductor. So the grid material requires good conductivity and corrosion resistance in addition to enough strength and stiffness. When fabricating battery grids, the selection of proper fiber volume percentage should be based on the comprehensive consideration of its influence on all above properties, should ensure the conductivity and corrosion resistance of the composite material from degrading too much, besides ensure the material to get expected reinforced effect.

The relation among tensile strength, elastic modulus, conductivity and the fiber volume percentage is shown in Fig.1, Fig.2 and Fig.3 respectively.

Tensile test was performed in a "AG-25TA" universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 1mm/min, with plate-like, dumb bell tensile sample having 40mm gauge length. The conductivity of C/Pb composite was measured with a solartron 7071 computer Voltmeter. The sample used for conductive test has the dimension of 3.2mm diameter and 100mm long. According to Fig.1, Fig.2 and Fig.3, the suitable fiber volume content is about 5%.

In the case of containing of 6% carbon fiber by volume, the C/Pb composite material is one times or more bigger than Pb-6% Sb alloy in strength, and the conductivity of C/Pb composite is also superior to that of Pb-6%Sb alloy, which is widely used for commercial grid at present.

3. Composite grid design

A new composite grid was designed to reduce weight by 25% with referring to the size of a commercial tubular positive grid. The transverse size of the main parts of the new one can be reduced proportionally, while the longitudinal size is kept as same as the commercial one.

4. Process

C/Pb composite material grid was fabricated by vacuum liquid infiltration. Carbon fibers pretreated by surface coating need to be aligned uniformly in grid model according to longitudinal direction of each part of the grid before infiltrating.

RESULTS

The C/Pb composite material grid made by the above method is show in Fig. 4(b), while Fig.4(a) gives a conventional alloy grid for comparing. In both directions of transverse and longitudinal, carbon fibers distribute rather well in the matrix, as shown in Fig.5.

The weight and constituent of the two kinds of grid are listed in Table 1. The data indicates that the weight of the composite grid is reduced by about 35%. The mechanical and physical properties of the new grid are superior to the ordinary Pb-6% Sb alloy grid, which is shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the tensile strength of the new grid increases by 1.5 times. A sample of failed composite material grid resulting from unsuitable control of process parameters is given as well (see Fig.6).

CONCLUSION

1. C/Pb composite grid can be successfully fabricated by vacuum liquid infiltration. Comparing with the commercial one, the weight of composite grid decreases by more than 35%, with obviously improved in mechanical property. A large amount of lead and antimony metal materials can be saved with the application of this new type of composite grid.
2. The pretreatment of carbon fibers is very important in preparing the composite grid.
3. The capacity of the new battery, in which C/Pb composite material containing of 6% carbon fiber by volume is used for the positive grid, increases 10% or more than conventional battery, so the new battery permits larger electric current to pass through while discharging. Other properties testing of the new battery is still underway.

The authors of this manuscript are (a) professor, (b) associate professor and (c) graduate student.

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Fig.1 Longitudinal tensile strength of C/Pb composite vs. volume fraction of carbon fiber (%)

Fig.2 longitudinal tensile modulus of C/Pb composite vs. volume fraction of carbon fiber (%)

Fig.3 conductivity of C/Pb composite vs. volume fraction of carbon fiber (%)

Fig.4 Appearance of the battery grid of C/Pb composite and Pb-Sb alloy

Fig.5 Distribution of carbon fiber in the grid of C/Pb composite

Fig.6